

DESIGN FOR CHRONIC ILLNESS

EXPLORING SERVICE SYSTEMS AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES FOR PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Our research focuses on designing new services and technologies to assist with the management of type 2 diabetes. Through an observational study, survey, and interviews, we identified that the patients who struggle most with management are those who lack social support. To combat this, we propose an intervention directly after diagnosis through a peer mentor service rooted within an online community for people with diabetes.

This paper presents a service framework for an online peer mentor community called CareMentors. A prototype was evaluated by 24 users through role-playing scenarios. The results suggest that mentor relationships are most beneficial to users when they are initially diagnosed or feel they are losing control. Many patients are also willing to participate as a mentor. Background checks and mentor training (for safety purposes), and providing a sense of anonymity, are found to be critical.

Keywords: Social Support, Diabetes, Chronic Illness, Healthcare, Peer Mentoring

INTRODUCTION

The U.S. National Center for Health Statistics defines a chronic illness as an illness lasting at least 3 months that does not often “resolve spontaneously, and [is] rarely cured completely” (CDC 2003). The 1998 U.S. National Medical Expenditure Panel Survey states, “the number of people with chronic illness in the U.S. alone is projected to reach 171 million by the year 2030” (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 1998). At some point, nearly everyone will encounter

a chronic illness either directly or through a family member or close acquaintance. It is estimated that 25.8 million people in the U.S. have diabetes, which is enough to fill 337 football stadiums. Worldwide, 150 million people have diabetes—18 times the population of New York City. This is expected to double by 2025. Of these cases, 90-95% are type 2 diabetes. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention call this an epidemic. In 2007, the U.S. spent \$174 billion dollars on diabetes treatment—that is enough to buy 743 jet airplanes. If a person can manage his type 2 diabetes well, he may not need medications and will encounter less or no complications (American Diabetes Association 2011).

These people with chronic illness, along with their families, are constantly confronted with health decisions without a doctor’s guidance. According to University of Pittsburgh social and behavioral scientist Jacqueline Dunbar-Jacob, poor management of chronic illness is often a result of errors and lack of understanding around prescriptions, side effects, and daily management regimen. Patients and families become tired of carrying out the management regimen, disagree about the disease or treatment, lack clinical support and illness education, or simply are not aware of what to do or how to monitor the proper management behavior for the illness (Dunbar-Jacob 2004).

Despite collaborative care between patients and health care providers, a large amount of care is left to the patient outside the physician’s office. In the best cases, health care providers offer patients self-management education. However, the concept of collaboration has not been implemented effectively. As Dunbar-Jacob illustrates, management practices

OUT OF CONTROL

are often widely varied, and less than half of U.S. patients with a chronic illness receive appropriate support and health management instructions. Without a firm grasp of the problem solving skills necessary to manage their illness, many patients are left to find and process information alone. To supplement the information given in the clinical setting, patients now use the Internet as a guide.

Many patients are turning to the Internet, specifically online support communities, for solutions. According to the 2009 Pew Internet and the American Life report on online health, 86% of adult Internet users with a chronic health condition have searched for health information online, and as a result, 40% of these users have then taken a health related action (Fox 2009). Patients are educating themselves on their illnesses and taking management steps through their own judgment. These findings suggest that many patients with chronic illnesses do not manage their health under the supervision of health care professionals.

In order to fill this gap in the care of patient with chronic illnesses, our project focuses on the challenges of lifestyle management outside of the doctor's office, with our focus being patients with type 2 diabetes. We explored the use of social communities for support immediately after the diagnosis of type 2 diabetes. Using a survey, interviews, and directed storytelling, we looked at the general patient experience from diagnosis to long-term management. The results suggest that patients who struggled with management often lacked social support from their doctor, family or friends. Hence, our design solution shifted from creating a tool for behavior change, and instead focused on creating an intervention of social support after diagnosis, with the goal that it will lead to better management in the long term.

A review of significant literature provided guidance for our research study. Many of the readings came from the fields of psychology, anthropology and sociology focused on health care and chronic illness. We also explored literature around social media, new technologies, and health care innovation. What we found is that peer support is key for lifestyle management. Peer support allows for storytelling,

which is incredibly important in coping with illness. Social communities are being used as a platform for these stories. Sharing a personal story is linked with improved health and chronic illness control, in part because stories help break down denial through engagement and identification between both the storyteller and the reader (Chen 2011).

According to a study, peer support, even through community health workers, has been shown to benefit health in many ways (Swider 2002). Specific to diabetes, these benefits include improved blood sugar control (Joshu 2007). Peer support has four key components: assistance in daily management, social and emotional support, linkage to clinical care, and ongoing support extended over time (Heisler 2006). What is unique about peer support is that it functions to supplement and extend formal primary care services—it does not replace the role of professional health care providers (see Figure 1).

Peer support can be a successful method to foster patient empowerment—helping patients discover and develop the capacity to be responsible for their own lives. Funnell and Anderson argue that patients are the experts on their lives, and they are the primary decision-makers in control of their illness (Funnell and Anderson 2002). They state “Intervention strategies that enable patients to make decisions about goals, therapeutic options, and self-care behaviors and to assume responsibility for daily diabetes care are effective in helping patients care for themselves.” Our project aims to utilize peer support, foster patient empowerment in care and create better management of diabetes.

METHODS

Our design process began with the interview of patients and key stakeholders. We then analyzed the data to identify salient needs of the patients. Based on the findings, design concepts were quickly generated around the identified needs. These concepts were sketched out in the form of a visual scenario. The final design involved a series of participatory co-design sessions with patients with type 2 diabetes. A prototype was then developed, and evaluated with 24 users.

Figure 1. What is unique about peer support is that it functions to complement, supplement and extend formal primary care services.

USER RESEARCH

'Think, Feel, Do' is a design method focused on understanding how thoughts, emotions, behaviors, physical reactions and environments all work together to affect a person's state of mind. In order to design a tool or a service for patients with type 2 diabetes, it was critical to develop an understanding of their day-to-day life. We looked for the subtleties in every user encounter through the following research activities:

- Observations of Online Communities
- User & Expert Interviews with Directed Storytelling
- Online Survey

OBSERVATIONS OF ONLINE COMMUNITIES

Before we started interviewing patients, we began an observational study of two online diabetic communities: www.tudiabetes.com and www.diabeticconnect.com. We followed conversations and users on these web sites, observing what was being talked about, shared, and taking note of the relationships people were forming. We found that certain patients take on a 'leadership/peer mentor' role by welcoming new members, listening to their stories around diagnosis and coping, and sharing their own experience. A number of patients dive into the community when they have a question, but then 'lurk' or remain inactive until they want to ask something

again. Frequently patients discussed topics other than their diabetes, while at the same time, many patients stated the online community was the only place they could discuss their diabetes and be understood.

INTERVIEWS & SURVEY

The online observations helped to provide a sense of why patients were using online social communities, and to highlight the most common struggles. By interviewing patients both face to face and via telephone, we were able to gather a more personal perspective on having type 2 diabetes. We also spoke to many patients who did not use online social communities, and launched a survey to gather a wider range of responses. We held several rounds of interviews (traditional interviews, follow-up interviews, occasional shadowing with a patient and her pharmacist over a year, then interviewing again during the design and testing stage). For the initial interviews, there were a couple rounds with 27 people (24 patients, 2 physicians and 1 nurse) and 57 survey participants (all patients). The findings provided larger support for what was discovered in the interviews. Below are the key insights and quotes.

Key Insights

- Patients use the Internet (often right after diagnosis) as their largest source of information.
- Support is critical directly after diagnosis for healthy coping and developing a care strategy.
- Diabetes is very personal and patients see themselves as solely responsible for their care.
- Patients question identity; many struggle with blame and coping.
- Feeling knowledgeable, in control, and responsible leads to patient empowerment.
- Support from doctors, family members, and friends leads to better management.
- Family or doctors may have different views of illness than the patient. This clash in beliefs can cause many serious problems.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Figure 2: Patterns that emerged from 27 Interviews: 24 patients, 2 doctors, 1 nurse; 57 Survey participants (all patients)

The results of observations of online communities, interviews, and survey data provided a meaningful yet complex picture of diabetes management. In order to develop a better understanding of the results and identify the salient patterns that would help us uncover opportunities for innovative intervention, we explored visual mapping of the key ideas found in results. Figure 2 shows the final diagram. Four major themes emerged: coping, support, information seeking, and management. Each theme is associated with a particular activity area of the patients.

The experience of initial diagnosis is found to be a significant pain point for our users—some patients were diagnosed over the phone, and others had spouses who ignored their diagnosis. How doctors treat the situation has a strong impact on next steps for the patient. Whether the patients receive support after diagnosis impacts their ability to cope, which affects how they choose to manage their illness. Finding helpful and reliable information right after diagnosis sets the stage for how patients decided to change their habits and tackle their care. Our interviewees (who either were still struggling with management, or who first struggled and later got on a better track of care) mentioned issues such as: not receiving social support, being guided towards diabetes education, or taught how to move forward after the diagnosis.

The general pattern is diagnosis, information seeking, education, then lifestyle changes. Yet not everyone makes those lifestyle changes. Some users talk about “taking control” and pushing forward with the desire to live well and change their lifestyle to “control diabetes.” Some struggle with this change, but they are determined and work towards it with small steps. Others deny the illness and ignore the condition, often until a complication arises and it scares them enough to make changes. Interviewees describe this as a “light bulb suddenly turning on” or simply a moment that scares them into making the changes. The moment of diagnosis is repeatedly described as either a successful guidance towards developing a care plan around diabetes, or a pain point that made the illness a struggle.

Based on these findings, we refined our design problem and decided to focus on supporting patients who are recently diagnosed with type 2 diabetes. We hypothesized that there is a missed opportunity for an intervention right after diagnosis, which would result in significant benefit for patients with type 2 diabetes to cope and manage their lifestyle in the long term.

NEW PROBLEM STATEMENT

What occurs during and directly after diagnosis of type 2 diabetes has a large impact on a patient's well-being

Figure 3: Example personas developed out of user research, mapped against a diagram of common experiences after diagnosis. Personas were associated with short stories, such as for Shauna: “Shauna was diagnosed over the phone, and her doctor takes little time to guide her. She has no social support, relies heavily on medication to manage her condition, and does not exercise”

and disease management. If patients do not receive understanding and support from their doctor and/or social network, their steps toward care can be stunted. A key to healthy coping and management is social support: the physical and emotional comfort given to us by our family, friends, co-workers, and others, as well as knowing that we are part of a community of people who care for and value us. Unfortunately, social support is not always provided by doctors, family and friends. Providing social support after diagnosis helps the patient learn daily management skills, provides emotional support and motivation, and leads to overall improvement. With our research, we explored service systems and new technologies to design a social support intervention for patients directly after diagnosis.

PERSONAS

Based on the digital observations, interviews and survey, we developed 4 personas and the common paths they take after diagnosis. People make certain choices in their next steps for care based on their level of support and their ability to cope with the diagnosis. By illustrating the current situation of these patients and mapping out their journey, we were able to see where breakdowns or problems were occurring for them. Our design targets Frank and Jason, the Late-Bloomer and the Reluctant patient, as these are the users closest to wavering and struggling with their diabetes. Achievers like Caitlin can easily use the design solution, and hopefully, the Shaunas who are in Denial can be steered towards support, acceptance, and better management (See Figure 3).

SCENARIO RESEARCH

In order to validate our research insights and concept ideas, we held concept scenario sessions both in person and online. We sketched out brief scenarios of an idea and shared them with users for reactions and feedback (See Figure 4 for an example). Below are the overall observations from the sessions:

- Participants respond positively to speaking with someone who has experienced diabetes.
- Participants want emotional support and understanding (not specific medical advice).
- Culture-specific mentors are good for issues such as food (both traditional cultural food and times of religious observation) and language barriers.
- Participants want their families to understand how best to help them.
- Participants want to share their stories and give back to their communities.
- Participants responded positively to community goal setting and mobile support.
- Emergency lines are a liability risk—they cannot replace proper care from a doctor.
- Participants want LOCAL support, but it must be safe.
- Participants want communication options for support matching.
- The program could be recommended at diagnosis, but then also reach out to the patient after a little time has passed (maybe within the first week).
- “I want the mentor relationship to form naturally. If it is a set match through a search only, with no options, then it could not be a good match. I need

a combination of searching, along with allowing the relationship to start through serendipity.”

- Mentors need to go through training and have a background check for safety.
- Mentors cannot give medical advice. Each body has specific needs. The mentor program is for providing emotional care, encouraging communication between the family, and providing guidance resources.
- “I want to give back as a mentor and help others to whom I relate.”

Figure 4: Scenario sketches, which were tested with users.

By performing this activity, we were able to reaffirm the need for social support directly after diagnosis. We identified the ideas that were not resonating well with patients. As a result, we narrowed our design solution

to a peer mentor matching service directly after diagnosis (See Figures 5-7).

DESIGN SOLUTION

After our research and participatory design exploration, we created CareMentors, a peer mentor service rooted within a social community for people with type 2 diabetes. After a user is diagnosed with type 2 diabetes, he or she is introduced to the service through brochures at the Doctor’s office. Nurses then input the patient’s contact information into the system. Within a week, CareMentors call the users to let them know they are not alone. The community is there to help. Users are matched with mentors who provide support and guidance concerning coping and learning about type 2 diabetes (See Figures 5-7).

Once the user logs into the community site, he or she can search for mentors by location, age, ethnicity, gender and/or a specific mentor focus. In addition, they can form more natural relationships by first participating in discussion boards with mentors. Once a mentor is chosen, the user can select his preferred communication style, and they begin conversations once a week, while personalizing their shared “My Mentor & I” space. Once a user has increased management skills and health, they can enroll in training to become a CareMentor for others.

Figure 5: CareMentors Model: Newly diagnosed Patient (top) is paired with care mentor (bottom), and over time becomes CareMentor (left)

Figure 6: CareMentors Service

Figure 7: CareMentors Experience

CareMentors aims to help users cope, feel understood, in control, more likely to make healthy choices and actively seek education to foster better management of their illness (See Figures 6 & 7).

EVALUATION & FINDINGS

We tested our prototype in person with four patients with diabetes, a diabetes pharmacist, and online with twenty-four patients from two online social diabetes communities. The prototype was a video scenario, which walked through the diagnosis of diabetes, joining CareMentors and eventually becoming a mentor. It included designs of the online community and highlighted several features. We did not build a fully functional online community because unless we had it embedded with diabetes educators or trained mentors, we could not test if our concept leads to better health and coping. Instead of building the functioning web site, we focused the goals of our evaluation on the different methods of interaction for finding and retaining a mentor (mentor search v.s. natural discussion), motivation to become involved as a peer mentor, and what elements make the online community valuable to patients.

We ran user testing sessions through role-playing scenarios both in person and online. The initial in-person sessions used paper screens, which we narrated, and the online survey used videos with audio. The user was introduced to the context: imagining they were just diagnosed, envisioning this is their current situation. When they reached the first touchpoint of the system, the brochure in the doctor's office, they were handed the brochure to examine and 'think aloud' about their reaction. We then moved to the website. The user was given two different options for finding a mentor. After exploring various aspects of the website, the user was brought out of the interface and into the ending of the scenario. With a mentor recommendation and a visit to the doctor, the user has the option to enter into mentor training and become a CareMentor in the community, cycling back in the process.

The user then reflected on the process, the mentor program and online community. The user answered questions about whether she felt it aided with coping, gaining better understanding of diabetes, and whether it might help her to live healthier. Through the user

testing sessions, we verified that CareMentors is most beneficial to users when they are initially diagnosed or when they feel they are losing control. One user said "I would work with a mentor if I was just diagnosed or if I felt I was not on track with my care." Once the patient feels stable, a user may step back from the mentor relationship and only use the general online community for support.

All users said if a health care provider or a friend recommended the CareMentors program, they would be more likely to join. Only two users said they would not want to use a mentor service. Users are willing and excited to give back to their community by becoming a mentor (thirteen users confirmed they would become a mentor if given the opportunity). Incentives such as insurance break or rewards also help to motivate participation. Users want to control and maintain a sense of anonymity in the community, and they want to be sure that CareMentors is vigilant with who becomes a mentor. They want background checks on mentors for safety, and to see detailed information about the mentor on the Mentor Profile page.

Study participants leaned towards letting the mentor relationship develop naturally in discussions, but they still felt the mentor search to be very important. It is useful when the user has a specific need or does not know where to start. Having the mentors express their personal selves on the Mentor Profile page is crucial to building trust with the user. The "My Mentor & I" page is also extremely valuable. This page is a log, a journal of the back and forth relationship and conversation. It is a place for users to express themselves and the mentor relationship. They suggested that it should be fun, joyful, funny, personalized, expressive, relaxed, creative, and controlled by the user and mentor.

CONCLUSION

People with type 2 diabetes need a design that will foster action within themselves. Over and over in our interviews, we would hear, "diabetes is a very individual illness," "diabetes is mine, I'm the only one who can control it." No matter how many tools are put in place to push patients to change their behavior, they will not change it if they do not want to. With behavior change, patients have to take very small

steps toward change, and it has to be of their own will. Many of our interviewees would describe a “light bulb moment in which I realized I needed to change or else I’d lose my leg or my sight or have a stroke” or even “my daughter was diagnosed with type 2 diabetes and I realized I had to change if I did not want her to have the same life I did.”

Peer support can be provided in many forms, but it will not reach the group who has not hit the light bulb moment. It can reach and help those who are very close to that moment (the Late-Bloomer persona in Figure 3), and people who struggle with control but are active in trying (the Reluctant persona).

The design solution presented in this case study is about people—creating a connection with someone else who has gone through the process of having type 2 diabetes. It is about creating spaces for patients to share their story with another, and knowing they are not alone, especially when they feel they do not get support from those around them. Beginning to address the shock of diabetes, and hoping to ease it with the comfort of a peer, is in hopes of fostering agency to make change. And no system or service will make a patient change— it has to come from within him or herself. The patient’s peer will be there to help along the way. Sometimes, just knowing the support is there, even if the patient never uses it, is the needed comfort.

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